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University-industry interactions: the role of university chairs in the management field¹

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Introduction

The request to demonstrate the societal impact of research is increasing everywhere (Muhonen et al., 2020). Since university-industry collaborations are expected to enhance economic development and achieve societal impact, diverse mechanisms have been put forward to channel those collaborations (Villani et al., 2017; Perkmann et al., 2021). However, not all of them have received the same attention in the literature. For example, several studies have documented the role of intermediary structures that facilitate technology transfer from universities to market (Siegel et al., 2004). Overall, the purpose of these intermediary structures, such as knowledge transfer offices (KTOs) is to facilitate scientists' knowledge commercialization and also to act as a liaison between science and businesses. While KTOs perform relatively good in promoting commercial transfer activities (e.g., intellectual property licenses or spin-off creations) and in channelling R&D contracts, they often fail to support and monitor scientists' engagement in other kind of collaborative science-society activities, resulting in a potential loss of financial rewards and social welfare (Fini et al., 2010). This is even more problematic in contexts where non-commercial activities are a prevalent mode of university-industry collaboration.

Against this background, it is crucial to devote more attention to alternative university intermediary mechanisms that facilitate and support meeting spaces to build relationships between researchers and companies and with the potential to house and boost non-commercial collaborations. One of this collaborative mechanism are university chairs, conceived as mechanisms providing 'hybrid spaces' to channel university-industry collaborations. To our knowledge, the role of these mechanisms is relatively understudied, which is surprising, as they allow bridging two different institutional logics, namely the academic logic and the commercial logic (Sauer mann & Stephan, 2013), acting as a boundary space between both logics (Perkmann et al., 2019).

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An important feature of chairs is that they allow to establish steady and stable spaces for fruitful collaborations that go beyond a single specific project or contract (Sanchis et al., 2014). Such repeated collaborations contribute to generate strong ties between scientists and business actors, nurturing shared meaning, trust and reciprocity among participants (Arza and Carattoli, 2017), eventually favouring the exchange of tacit knowledge between the parties. As opposed to KTOs, chairs organise other type of ‘softer’ activities (e.g., conferences, seminars, science communication activities) around a specific topic or field, in line with the interests of the promoters. In this project, we put the focus on university chairs as an understudied mechanism aimed at bringing together academics and business actors under a common space for collaboration. We expect chairs to be crucial instruments to channelize university-industry collaborations around specific topics of interest, in particular, in contexts dominated by non-commercial forms of collaboration.

Context

We frame our study within the field of management for different reasons. First, the field of management has received longstanding critics for its apparent remoteness from the practical problems encountered by managers. This disconnection, coined as the ‘research-practice gap’ or the ‘rigour-relevance gap’ (Banks et al., 2016), is still a current and major issue despite the sizeable body of academic studies aimed at addressing it (Huffman & Benson, 2021). Empirical evidence is scarce despite the extent literature on this topic, characterised by fragmented and often speculative, rather than grounded in solid empirical data (De Frutos-Belizón et al., 2019). Second, it is an interesting field for analysing university-industry collaborations because of its potential to impact any type of organisation through the provision to top managers of well-informed strategic decisions, which ultimately increases firms’ performance and competitiveness. Third, knowledge produced by management scholars does not fit into the (commercial) technology transfer model, but on other transfer approaches based on (softer) knowledge exchange channels such as consultancy, informal advice or seminars. All these reasons provide support to make the case for studying the role of university chairs in connecting university management scholars and firms’ managers.

Research objectives and model

In this research we aim at exploring whether (and how) management university chairs function as hybrid formal structures for establishing collaborations between research groups and top management teams. We expect university chairs to have the potential of being an effective mechanism through which to conduct actions aimed at fostering the transfer and exchange of knowledge between management scholars and top managers.

We tackle this issue through two specific objectives. The first is to explore how university chairs are managed, by addressing why and how the chair was created, its composition, the main challenges faced, and the type of activities organised. The second specific is to identify and analyse specific collaborations channeled through the chair and the actors involved. Understanding how specific collaborations are established between management researchers (or research groups) and top managers (or TMT) includes delving on what was the purpose of the specific collaboration, the activities conducted, the actors involved, how the collaboration initiated and evolved, the barriers perceived for collaborating (if any) and the benefits perceived.

The literature review conducted allows to identify the key elements to address our objectives. Figure 1 depicts the conceptual model that guides our research towards a better understanding of whether (and how) university chairs fulfil their function of connecting science and society.

Figure 1. Summary of the conceptual model

Methods

In this research we will focus on different unit of analysis (the chair, specific collaborations and actors involved in the chair), which allows to gather a comprehensive understanding on the chairs as hybrid structures to channel university-industry collaborations. We will rely on secondary data (reports and information available on the chairs) and on a qualitative study based on semi-structured interviews and non-participatory observation. Focusing on the chairs will provide information about management and functioning, allowing to look for heterogeneity but also similarities across chairs. Analysing specific collaborations established through the chair will allow to identify the process and conditions through which knowledge is transferred and exchanged, as well as identifying heterogeneity (or similarities) across the cases analysed. Addressing the actors involved in a chair will allow to better understand academic(s) and manager(s) motivations and perceived benefits from been involved in the chair.

Expected contributions

We expect to provide insights of whether (and how) chairs contribute to bring closer the supply-side (academics) and demand-side (top managers), boosting interactions and knowledge exchange. Against this background, our academic contribution is threefold: (1) analysing an understudied phenomenon (university chairs as a mechanism for facilitating university-industry interactions), (2) in a field (management) blamed by its disconnection from the business domain and where empirical evidence is barely non-existent, (3) by providing a holistic approach that includes both demand and supply sides of collaborations.

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